

Computation of Geometric Series: A New Approach

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a technique for the computation of novel geometric series that is used for application of computational science. Computational science is a rapidly growing multi-and inter-disciplinary area where science and technology and its collaboration use advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real-life problems. Also, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. For this purpose, a new generalized geometric series is introduced in this article.

MSC Classification codes: 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computing, geometric progression, summation

1. Introduction

Geometric series played a vital role in differential and integral calculus at the earlier stage of development and still continues as an important part of the study in science, engineering, management and its applications. In this article, a new geometric series [1-9] is constructed for application [10] of computational science and engineering.

2. Novel Geometric Series

Let $W = \{0,1,2,3, \dots\}$, $k \& p_i \in W$, and $p_0 = 1$. The generalized geometric series is:

$$\left(\sum_{j_k=0}^{p_k-1} x^{j_k(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i)} \right) \left(\sum_{j_{k+1}=0}^{p_{k+1}-1} x^{j_{k+1}(\prod_{i=1}^k p_i)} \right) \dots \left(\sum_{j_n=0}^{p_n-1} x^{j_n(\prod_{i=1}^{n-1} p_i)} \right) =$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\prod_{i=k}^n p_i - 1} x^{j(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i)} = \frac{x^{\prod_{i=1}^n p_i} - 1}{x^{\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} p_i} - 1}, x \neq 1 \text{ or } p_i \neq 0 \text{ for } x^{p_i}.$$

Now, let us find the different types of geometric series by substituting $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ in the above-mentioned geometric series.

Let $k = 1$.

$$\left(\sum_{j_1=0}^{p_1-1} x^{j_1} \right) \left(\sum_{j_2=0}^{p_2-1} x^{j_2 p_1} \right) \dots \left(\sum_{j_n=0}^{p_n-1} x^{j_n p_1 p_2 \dots p_{n-1}} \right) = \sum_{j=0}^{p_1 p_2 \dots p_n - 1} x^j = \frac{x^{p_1 p_2 \dots p_n} - 1}{x - 1}, x \neq 1.$$

Let $k = 2$.

$$\left(\sum_{j_2=0}^{p_2-1} x^{j_2 p_1} \right) \left(\sum_{j_3=0}^{p_3-1} x^{j_3 p_1 p_2} \right) \dots \left(\sum_{j_n=0}^{p_n-1} x^{j_n p_1 p_2 \dots p_{n-1}} \right) = \sum_{j=0}^{p_2 \dots p_n - 1} x^{j p_1} = \frac{x^{p_1 p_2 \dots p_n} - 1}{x^{p_1} - 1},$$

$p_1 \neq 0$.

We can continue these steps upto $k = n$.

Let $k = n$.

$$\left(\sum_{j_n=0}^{p_n-1} x^{j_n p_1 p_2 \cdots p_{n-1}} \right) = \frac{x^{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_n} - 1}{x^{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_{n-1}} - 1}, p_1 p_2 \cdots p_{n-1} \neq 0.$$

3. Conclusion

This article provides the novel geometric series and its summations for mathematical and computational applications. Also, this idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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